

FOOD CONSUMPTION PATTERNS, DIETARY DIVERSITY OF ADOLESCENTS AND ITS EFFECTS ON THEIR NUTRITIONAL STATUS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THREE LGAS OF BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

¹Donald-Ase, Mary, ²Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, ³Promise, Vivian Ibienebakabobo, ⁴Alikali, Ojochegbe Joy, ^{*5}Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and ⁶Afam-Anene, Olivia

¹Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics, Faculty of Health Sciences, Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State

²Nutrition and Dietetics Department, Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State

³Department of Public Health, Faculty of Health Sciences, Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State

⁴Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics, Faculty of Health Sciences, Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State

⁵Multidisciplinary Unit, West African Society of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition, Abuja FCT Research Wing, Distributions.Nigeria Limited, Umuahia, Abia State

Department of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State

⁶Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics, Faculty of Health Sciences, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State

***Corresponding Email:** trustjah.allison.186731@unn.edu.ng

Phone Number: +2348166282392

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Keywords: <i>Food, Consumption Patterns, Dietary, Diversity, Nutritional Status</i>	Abstract: <i>Adolescence is a period of growth and development between childhood and adulthood, it is a period of opportunity to shape healthy eating pattern and diversification of diet to establish a healthy food consumption habits to improve nutritional status. The objective of this study is to assess the food consumption patterns, dietary diversity and its effects on the nutritional status of adolescents in three LGAs of Bayelsa State. A total of 50 students each were selected from one girl's secondary school, one boy's secondary school and one mixed school in Ogbia and Sagbama LGAs. Four secondary schools were selected from Yenagoa LGA because it</i>
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the State Capital that housed majority of the schools where 50 students each were selected from one girl's secondary school, one boy's secondary school and two mixed school, giving a total of 500 students. A well-structured questionnaire was designed to elicit information on the demographic and socioeconomic status of the student's parents, dietary diversity score, measured by using simple count of the adolescent's food items consumed over the last 24 hours. Information obtained were analyzed using the Pearson Correlation between Food Diversity of the adolescent's diet and their nutritional status. The result of the BMI showed that 57 of the adolescents were underweight, 437 were of normal weight, 4 were overweight, while 2 were obese, the diversity of their diet was graded as very low, low, medium and high if less than 4 food groups, 4 to 5 food groups, 6 to 7 food groups more than 8 food groups were consumed, respectively. The study revealed that there is a statistically significant high level of positive relationship between BMI and adolescent dietary diversity.

Introduction

Despite the importance of nutrition for adolescents' current and future health, many adolescents still consume diets that are not consistent with dietary guidelines. For example, adolescents tend to have lower than desirable intakes of fruits, vegetables, dairy products, and whole grains but higher than desirable intakes of soft drinks, confectionery and fast foods (Keats, Rappaport and Jain, 2018). Consequently, many adolescents fall short of achieving optimal nutrient intakes for good health and development. (Keats, et.al., 2018). An adolescent is a person who is no longer a child and at the same time, cannot be considered an adult. Adolescence is a period of growth and development between childhood and adulthood, adolescents are young people between the ages of 10 and 19 years and are often thought of as a healthy group. An adolescent is a juvenile

between the onset of puberty and maturity. (Jaworska, Natalia and MacQueen, 2015), identifies adolescence as the period in human growth and development that occurs after childhood and before adulthood. It represents one of the critical transitions in the life span and is characterized by a pace in growth and change (Keats, et.al. 2018).

The nutritional requirements of adolescents are influenced primarily by their growth rate, their nutrient needs and this differs with regard to sex and age. As a result, nutritional requirements of some nutrients like iron and calcium are at risk of deficiency. Increased nutritional needs in adolescence is due to increased growth rate and body composition changes and these needs can be met by the adolescents' food choices and nutrient intake, improper food choices results in malnutrition with its grave consequences, (Alsubaie, 2017). Food consumption patterns

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and dietary diversity are vital sources to improve the nutritional status of adolescents. Severe malnutrition also can adversely delay the onset and progression of puberty, (Alsubaie, 2017).

The problems of Adolescent food consumption lies in the poor food consumption patterns among adolescents in secondary schools. The Adolescents dietary diversity impact lies in their poor and inadequate diversity of their diet. The poor food consumption patterns of the adolescents' impact on their nutritional status, leading to a variety of health issues, including undernutrition, overnutrition, and micronutrient deficiencies, which can have long-term consequences for their health and well-being.

Methodology

Study Area

Sampling technique was used in selecting the sample. Students were selected from the Senior Secondary School Classes (from SSS 1 to 3) using simple random sampling. Three Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State were selected for the study. The Local Government Areas were Yenagoa LGA, Ogbia LGA and Sagbama LGA through balloting. Ten secondary schools were randomly selected from the LGAs and fifty students each were randomly selected from the ten secondary schools.

Population of Study

Yenagoa LGA: A total of 50 students each were selected from one girl's secondary school, one boy's secondary school and two mixed school,

making a total of 200 students. Four secondary schools were selected from Yenagoa LGA because it the State Capital that housed majority of the schools.

Ogbia LGA: A total of 50 students each were selected from one girl's secondary school, one boy's secondary school and one mixed school, a total of 150 students.

Sagbama LGA: A total of 50 students each were selected from one girl's secondary school, one boy's secondary school and one mixed school, a total of 150 students.

Survey Design

The study was a cross sectional study using secondary school students in the selected schools.

Sample Selection

A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents from the secondary schools of three male schools, three female schools and four mixed schools. A total of 25 males and 25 females each were selected from the four mixed schools to make a total of 200 students while a total of 50 students each were selected from the three male and female schools to make a total of 150 males and 150 females. The final number of students was 250 males and females respectively.

Validation of Instrument

A preliminary visit was made to the schools to obtain permission from the school authorities and consent from the students. The structured questionnaires were pretested with ten

adolescents from five Secondary Schools in Kolokuma Opokuma LGA, which is different from the research area and respondents have similar characteristics with the population of the study.

Data Collection Methods

Three Research assistants were trained before data collection to help in the process and ensure consistency and accuracy, during the process of data collection, the research assistants were further trained on using illustrations to assist respondents in reporting on their food types consumed.

The adolescents were visited in their schools and questionnaires were given to them to fill and explanations made. Weight and height measurements were done using standard methods of (WHO, 2016).

Questionnaire: A well-structured questionnaire was designed to elicit information on the demographic and socioeconomic status of their parents and 24 hour dietary recall from the adolescents.

Anthropometric Measurement: Individual measurements of the weight and height were

Body Mass Index (BMI) Classification

Category	BMI range – kg/m²
Underweight	< 18.5
Normal (healthy weight)	18.5 - 24.9
Overweight	25.0 - 29.9
Obesity Grade I (Moderately obese)	30.0 - 34.9

Source: World Health Organization, Global Database on Body Mass Index, (2012)

carried out to estimate their Body Mass Index (BMI) which was compared to BMI reference standards.

Height: Height measurement was done according to the method as described by (Afam-Anene, Ifenacho and Iwuchukwu, 2015). Height was measured with wooden wall meter rule. The subject was asked to stand straight on a flat floor with shoes removed, feet put together and arms hanging loosely by the sides. Heels, buttocks and upper back were in contact with the wall. Recording was done to the nearest 0.1cm.

Weight: This was done using the method also described by (Afam-Anene, Ifenacho and Iwuchukwu, 2015). The subject was asked to stand on the weighing scale with shoes removed. Measurement was done with minimum clothing; readings were taken to the nearest 0.1kg.

Body Mass Index (BMI): Body Mass Index (BMI, Kg/m²) of the adolescents were determined by dividing weight in Kg by height (m²) squared and classified as underweight (<18.5), normal weight (18.5 – 24.9), overweight (25.0 – 29.9), obesity grade 1 (30.0 – 34.9) using, WHO (2012) classification.

24- hour dietary recall: This is a structured interview intended to capture detailed

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information about all foods and beverages consumed by the respondent in the past 24 hours, most commonly, from midnight to midnight of the previous day. The 24-hour Dietary Recall method provides comprehensive, quantitative information on individual diets by querying respondents about the type and quantity of all food intakes during the period (Gibson & Ferguson, 2008). The 24-hour diet recall relies on a trained interviewer, an accurate memory of intake, an ability to estimate portion size, and the interviewee's reliability to not misreport (Gibson, Charrondiere and Bell, 2017). The respondents were interviewed and record of their food intake in the last 24 hours were taken, the interview included the description of the foods eaten, the name, the cooking methods and questions were also asked to know the specific food groups in the meals.

Dietary diversity score (DDS): This was measured using simple count of the individual adolescent's food item consumed over the last 24 hours. It was calculated by summing up the

number of food groups consumed which includes cereals/roots, vegetables, fruits, legumes, meat/fish/egg & milk/dairy products, the food groups eaten were taken into count. And the diversity of their diet were graded as low, when less than 4 food groups were consumed, medium when 4 to 5 food groups were consumed and high when more than 5 food groups were consumed (Fitzgerald, Heary, Nixon and Kelly, 2010).

Calculation of dietary diversity score: The dietary diversity was assessed from the 24hours dietary recall. It was gotten by summing the number of food groups consumed during the past 24 hours. Food groups considered were a minimum of four food groups and a point was recorded to each food group consumed over the reference period and the sum of all the points were calculated for the dietary diversity score for the adolescents. The respondents were classified into low dietary diversity, medium dietary diversity and high dietary diversity respectively as shown below.

Dietary diversity score

Very Low DD <4 food (groups)	Low DD 5- 6 food (groups)	Medium DD 7-8 food (groups)	High DD >8 food groups
Cereals	Cereals	Cereals	Cereals (pastas, rice, bread)
Fish and sea foods (crayfish, oysters, prawns)	Vit. A rich Fruits and Vegetables	Vit. A rich Fruits and Vegetables	Vit. A rich Fruits and Vegetables
Milk and milk products	Fish and sea foods prawn, (crayfish, oysters)	Sugar/sweets (sweets, sweeteners, sugars	Root and Tubers (yam, cocoyam, potatoes, etc)

Meat and Poultry	Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts, nuts)	Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts)	Fish and sea foods, prawn (crayfish, oysters)
	Meat and poultry	Oils/Fats (butter, palm oil margarine, vegetable)	Milk and Milk Products
	Oils	Milk and Milk Products	Beverages
		Fish and sea foods (crayfish, oysters, prawns)	Meat/Poultry
		Root and Tubers (yam, cocoyam, potatoes, etc)	Sugar/sweets (sweets, sweeteners, sugars)
			Oils/Fats (butter, margarine, vegetable & palm oils)
			Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts, nuts)
			Eggs

Source: FAO, 2006

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Adolescents

Table 1 indicates the demographic characteristics of the adolescents. Analysis of the table shows that 14% of the adolescents were above 19years, 20% were between (18-19years), 36% were

within age range of (16-17 years), while 30% were of the age range of (14-15years). The predominant religion was Christianity (88%) with very few (12%) belonging to Islamic Sect. Most (40%) of the adolescents were in SSS III, while 38% were in SSS II and 22% were in SSS I classes.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Adolescents

Variables	Frequency (N)	Percentage %
Age (years)		
14-15	150	30
16-17	180	36
18-19	100	20
> 19	70	14
Total	500	100%
Sex		
Male	250	50
Female	250	50
Total	500	100%
Religion		
Christianity	444	88
Islam	56	12
Total	500	100%
Classes		
SS1	110	22
SS2	189	38
SS3	201	40
Total	500	100%

Table 2: Socio economic characteristics of the respondent's parents

Table 2: show the socio economic characteristics of the respondents' parents. It indicated that 8% of the fathers and 8.5% of the mothers were farmers, 17.6% of the fathers and 14.2% of the mothers were traders, also, 4% of the fathers and 6.5% of the mothers were pensioners, 10.4% of the fathers and 9.6% of the

mothers were into business and were self-employed, while 10% of the fathers and 11.2% of the mothers were civil servants. Also in the table, 7% of the fathers and 8% of the mothers had no formal education, 12% of the fathers and 10% of the mothers had primary education and 17.6% of the fathers and 20.4% of the mothers had secondary education, while 13.4% of the fathers and 11.6% of the mothers had tertiary education.

Table 2: Socio economic characteristics of the respondent’s parents

Variables	Father		Mother		Total	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Occupation of parents						
Farming	40	8	43	8.5	83	16.5
Trading	88	17.6	70	14.2	158	31.8
Pensioner	20	4.0	33	6.5	53	10.5
Others (Business/Self-employed)	52	10.4	48	9.6	100	20.0
Civil servant	50	10	56	11.2	106	21.2
Level of education of parents						
No formal education	35	7	40	8	75	15
Primary	60	12	55	10	110	22
Secondary	88	17.6	102	20.4	190	38
Tertiary	67	13.4	58	11.6	125	25

Table 3: Family history of the respondents

The table presents the family history of the respondents. Analysis of the table indicates that 5% of the males and 4% of the females have polygamous families, while 45% of the males and 46% of the females have monogamous families. It also showed that 11.2% of the males and 10.6%

of the females had one adolescent in their families, 16% of the males and 17% of the females had two adolescents and 10.4% of the males and 10.8% of the females had three adolescents, while 12% of the males and females respectively had four adolescents in their families.

Table 3: Family history of the respondents

Variables	Male		Female		Total	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Family Type						
Polygamous	25	5	20	4	45	9
Monogamous	225	45	230	46	455	91
Number of 10years to 19years in the family						
One	56	11.2	53	10.6	109	21.8
Two	80	16	85	17	165	33
Three	52	10.4	54	10.8	106	21.2
Four	60	12	60	12	120	24

Table 4: Food consumption pattern of the respondents

Table 4- shows the food consumption pattern of the respondents, which indicated that 9.5% of the students drinks about 1,000mls of water daily, while 62% drink more than 1,500mls of water daily. 4.0% of the males and 6.5% of the females eats food in the restaurants every day, while 10.4% of the males and 9.6% of the females

visits restaurants routinely. The table also indicated that the reasons given for skipping meals were lack of time to prepare meals by 2.8% and 4.4% males and females respectively and Inability to afford three meals per day by 15.6% males and 15.4% females while 13.6% of the males and 13.4% of the females skip meals because it is a general habit.

Table 4: Food consumption pattern of the respondents

Variables	Males		Females		Total	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Quantity of water taken in a day						
1,000mls	26	5.1	22	4.4	48	9.5
1,500mls	74	14.9	68	13.6	142	28.5
More than 1,500mls	150	30.0	160	32.0	310	62.0
Drinks taken at meal and after meal						
Water	208	41.6	216	43.1	424	84.7
Sweetened/carbonated drinks	8	1.6	12	2.4	20	4.0
Juice	18	3.6	14	2.9	32	6.5
Cocoa Beverage	16	3.2	8	1.6	24	4.8
Times foods were eaten in the restaurants						
Everyday	20	4.0	33	6.5	53	10.5
Two or more times a week	40	8.0	43	8.5	83	16.5
Weekly	50	10.0	56	11.2	106	21.2
Rarely	88	17.6	70	14.2	158	31.8
Routinely	52	10.4	48	9.6	100	20.0
Times fruits/vegetables are consumed with meals						
Always	26	5.2	24	4.8	50	10.0
Frequently	37	7.4	42	8.4	79	15.8
Sometimes	45	9.0	46	9.2	91	18.2
Rarely	70	14.0	58	11.6	128	25.6
Never	72	14.4	80	16.0	152	30.4

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Time you consume fruits

Often	180	36.0	187	37.4	367	73.4
Sometimes	68	13.6	61	12.2	129	25.8
Never	2	0.4	2	0.4	4	0.8

Number of times you consume vegetables

Often	160	32.0	201	40.2	361	72.2
Sometimes	86	17.2	49	9.8	135	27.0
Never	4	0.8	0	0	4	0.8

Frequency of legumes consumption

Often	203	40.6	196	39.2	399	79.8
Sometimes	41	8.2	46	9.2	87	17.4
Never	6	1.2	8	1.6	14	2.8

Frequency of dairy Products consumption

Cheese	28	5.6	31	6.2	59	11.8
Yoghurt	56	11.2	60	12.0	116	23.2
Milk and other milk products	166	33.2	159	31.8	325	65.0

Frequency of fats and oils consumption

Often	232	46.4	238	47.6	470	94
Sometimes	18	3.6	12	2.4	30	6
Never	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 5 - Income of parents and number of times foods are eaten daily in the households

Table 5 - The study showed that 3.6% of the respondent’s parents earned about ₦50,000

monthly, while the parents of 105 respondents earn more than ₦130,000 monthly, 2.2% of the respondents accepted that they eat once daily, 84.8% eat twice daily, 9.0% eat three times daily, while 3.2% eat more than 4 times daily

Table 5 - Income of parents and number of times foods are eaten daily in the households

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Variables	Male		Female		Total	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Average monthly income of parents (Naira)						
<50,000	8	1.6	10	2	18	3.6
51,000 – 100,000	40	8	42	8.4	82	16.4
100,000 – 130,000	145	29	150	30	295	59
>130,000	50	10	55	11	105	21
Times foods are eaten in a day						
Once	6	1.2	5	1.0	11	2.2
Twice	208	41.6	216	43.2	424	84.8
Three times	20	4.0	25	5.0	45	9.0
More than three times	4	0.8	12	2.4	16	3.2

Figure 6a: Diversity of the adolescent’s diet and their nutritional status

This table indicates the diversity of the adolescent’s diet. the diversity of their diet was graded as very low, if less than 4 food groups were consumed, low if 4 to 5 food groups were consumed, medium if 6 to 7 food groups were

consumed and high when more than 8 food groups were consumed, 10% of the respondents consumed 4 food groups, 80.6% consumed about 5 to 6 food groups, 19.4% consumed 7 to 8 food groups while, 4% consumed more than 8 food groups.

Figure 6a: Diversity of the adolescent’s diet and their nutritional status

Table 6b: Correlations between Diversity of the adolescent’s diet and their nutritional status

The correlation result showed a statistically significant high level of positive relationship

between the students’ Body Mass Index and adolescent dietary diversity ($p = 0.019$, $r = 0.981$).

Table 6b: Correlations between Diversity of the adolescent’s diet and their nutritional status

		Adolescent dietary diversity	BMI
Adolescent dietary diversity	Pearson Correlation	1	.981*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.019
	N	4	4
BMI	Pearson Correlation	.981*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019	
	N	4	4

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figure 7: Body Mass Index Status of the respondents

Analysis of the BMI Status showed that 11.4% of the adolescents were underweight, 87.4% were of

normal weight, 0.8% were overweight, while 0.4% were obese

Figure 7: Body Mass Index Status of the respondents

Table 8: 24 Hour dietary recall table

Table 9- presents the 24 hour dietary recall of the respondents, the analysis indicates that 30.0% of the respondents ate roots and tubers, 33.2 ate

Table 8: The 24hour Dietary Recall of the respondents

Food Groups	Males	Females	Total
Root and Tubers (yam, cocoyam, potatoes, etc)	73 (14.6%)	78 (15.6%)	151 (30.0%)
Fish and sea foods (crayfish, oysters, prawns, etc)	81 (16.2%)	85 (17.0%)	166 (33.2%)
Cereals (pastas, rice, bread, biscuits, etc)	72 (14.4%)	74 (14.8%)	146 (29.2%)
Milk and Milk Products (ice creams, etc)	82 (16.4%)	80 (16.0%)	162 (32.4%)
Vegetables/Fruits (oranges, banana, carrots, etc)	95 (19.0%)	98 (19.6%)	193 (38.6%)
Meat/Poultry (chicken, etc)	121 (24.2%)	121 (24.2%)	242 (48.4%)
Sugar/sweets (sweets, sweeteners, sugars, etc)	71 (14.2%)	74 (14.8%)	145 (29.0%)

fish and sea foods within the last 24 hours, while 29.2% ate cereals. Most of the respondents 48.4% consumed meat and poultry products, while majority of them 75.0% consumed pulses, legumes and nuts, 35.6% ate eggs.

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Oils/Fats (butter, margarine, vegetable & palm oils)	65 (13.0%)	67 (13.4%)	132 (26.4%)
Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts, nuts, etc)	188 (37.6%)	187 (37.4%)	275 (75.0%)
Eggs	90 (18.0%)	88 (17.6%)	178 (35.6%)

Discussions

All respondents used were adolescents and most (86%) were within the age range of 14-19 years. Jaworska, et.al., (2015), identifies adolescence as the period in human growth and development that occurs after childhood and before adulthood. An adolescent is a juvenile between the onset of puberty and maturity. According to (Stehlik and Thomas, 2018) on their study on "Educational Philosophy for 21st Century Teachers", states that adolescence is a period of transitional stage of physical and psychological development which occurs during puberty to adulthood, which is usually associated with the teenage years. Results in this study showed that majority (88%) of the respondents were Christians while 12% practice Islam. The adolescent's religion was investigated to find out the effect of their religion on food choices because some culture and religion have restrictions concerning what foods are acceptable is their diets. For example the Buddhists are generally vegetarians, an Adventist, even when they eat meat, will never eat pork and sea foods, it stood against their religious beliefs (Dinu, Monica and Abbate, 2017), most foods that are forbidden by the above factors are foods that are nutritionally rich and should be eaten by the adolescents, so that the

nutritional benefits are not being denied. According to Kontis, Bennett and Mathers, (2017) in the study on "Future life expectancy in 35 industrialized countries", adequate nutrient intake is critical at all stages of life especially during the adolescent years, it is not just to facilitate rapid physiological growth and development but also serves as a foundation to good health in the later life. The quality of food consumed during the adolescent years have long-term effects on the health and well-being of an individual throughout life, therefore it is important to prioritize the nutritional needs of adolescents to provide clear dietary guidance. Most (85%) of the respondent parents had different forms of education and this can have effects on their income and purchasing power, even those with high income does not mean that they have good knowledge of nutrition (Stroud, 2013). The level of nutrition education can influence dietary behaviour of people, this is because knowledge about health lead to direct positive actions to improve health, (Vaitkeviciute, Ball, and Harris, 2015). The study of Spronk, Kullen and Burdon, (2014), on the "Relationship between nutrition knowledge and dietary intake", demonstrated that education help to improve nutrition knowledge, attitude, and diet quality. In the study on "Effectiveness of

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a school-based intervention on knowledge, attitude and practice on healthy lifestyle and body composition in Malaysian adolescents” by Sharif, Chin and Mohd, (2020), there was a significant improvement in the mean nutrition knowledge score of 1.80 after the implementation of the intervention compared to the control group.

The family type of the respondents also have direct effect on the adolescents’ food choices and eating habits and implications on their nutritional status, many (91%) have a monogamous family while (9%) have polygamous family life. The family unit determines the variety, quality and quantity of food consumed in the family, also, how much people eat can be influenced by how much other people are eating and how many people are eating together, this has to do with harmonious living, (AL-Sharfi, 2015). Polygamous families have more people to provide for in the family, without enough income there would be no proper food choices. Most times, due to the number of people in the home, there is no enough food available to meet the nutritional needs of all individual present in the family, leading to poor food choices.

Many of the respondents (62%) takes more than 1,500mls of water daily, the practice is commendable and should be encouraged. Water is for hydration and is very important for optimum health and it is necessary to drink enough water daily, (Jequier and Constant, 2010). Most of the adolescents in this study took enough water daily for hydration and optimum

health, the level of knowledge resulted from effective health education in schools, community and campaigns, focusing on delivering the message to influence adolescents. This ongoing educational initiatives and campaigns played pivotal roles in maintaining high levels of awareness and proper hydration practices among young people. Some of the respondents parents earn about N50,000 monthly, while some earn more than N130,000, this mean that their family’s income can affects the purchase of the desired food stuffs affecting the availability and accessibility of foods in the family, (Beck, Iturralde and Haya-Fisher, 2019).

There were prevalence of underweight, overweight and obesity, while normal weight was (87.4%) respondents in this study. According to WHO (2017), healthy growth and development essentially need an adequate diet which includes a variety of foods from different food groups. A cross sectional study on adolescents aged 15 to 18 years in Ambo and Chiro town in Ethiopia reported prevalence of underweight to be 24.4% and 27.5% respectively, (Eshetu, 2015). A study conducted in Southern Ethiopia on the “Overweight and Undernutrition in the Cases of School-Going Adolescents in Wolaita Sodo Town”, stated that the prevalence of undernutrition was more or less comparable to the study conducted in Addis Ababa, the prevalence of thinness and stunting was 7.2% and 6.2% respectively (Gebreyohannes, Solomon Shiferaw and Demtsu, 2014). Dambhare, Bharambe and Mehendale, (2010) in the study “Nutrition and Health Status of Adolescents in a

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Private Secondary School in Port Harcourt” reported 48.3% of the adolescents were normal weight, none was overweight and obese and 51.7% were underweight. The prevalence was much lower than reports from previous studies in Niger Delta, South Eastern Nigeria which is similar to the findings in Markudi, Benue state (Goon, Toriola and Shaw, 2011). Eating food from more food groups provides an adequate diet and is necessary for proper growth and development in the lives of adolescents. It is also vital in the effort to combat malnutrition (Neumark-Sztainer, Wall and Larson, 2011).

The 24 hour dietary recall revealed consumption of meat, poultry, fish and sea foods quantity consumed might not be adequate, but these foods are readily available in the locality and are good sources of protein, vitamins and minerals and needed to be consumed. It is necessary to consume at least 2 to 3 servings of protein rich foods daily and proteins are essential for the growth and repair of body cells to provides energy in the absence of carbohydrates and when eaten in excess is converted to fat (Fitzgerald, *et. al.*, 2010). Meats contributed significantly to zinc and vitamin B-12 intakes, and to a lesser extent to iron intakes. Other studies have demonstrated a high contribution of meats to iron, zinc and vitamin B-12 intakes (Welch, Fransen and Jenab, 2009). However, in the study on the “Variation in intakes of calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, iron and potassium in 10 countries in the European”, Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition by Welch, *et.al.*, (2009), the contribution of meats to iron was lower than

the contribution of cereals, rice, bread, or pastas for all ethnic-sex groups, which may be in part due to mandatory fortification of cereal and grain foods, despite this finding, it is important to consider that the bioavailability of heme iron from red meat is far greater than that of non-heme iron. Most of the respondents consumed meat and poultry products, while majority of them consumed pulses, legumes, nuts, and eggs, the diversity of the adolescent’s diet was graded as very low, if less than 4 food groups were consumed, low if 4 to 5 food groups were consumed, medium if 6 to 7 food groups were consumed and high when more than 8 food groups were consumed, 10% of the respondents consumed 4 food groups, 80.6% consumed about 5 to 6 food groups, 19.4% consumed 7 to 8 food groups while, 4% consumed more than 8 food groups. Meats contribute significantly to zinc and vitamin B-12 intakes, and iron intakes, (Cosgrove, Flynn and Kiely 2005). However, in the study on, “Contribution of meat to vitamin B-12, iron, and zinc intakes in five ethnic groups in the U.S, Implications for developing food-based dietary guidelines”, the iron content in meat was lower than the iron content in cereals, rice, bread, or pastas for all ethnic-sex groups, this may be due to the mandatory fortification of cereal and grain foods. Protein is important for adolescents, whose bodies are growing and changing daily, a lack of protein in the diet can slow growth, reduce muscle mass, lower immunity, lack of enough protein in the adolescents’ diet can lead to retarded growth, poor wound healing and reduced energy, if the

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food contains too much energy there would be overweight (Saunders 2010).

Limitations of Study

- i. The information gathered from the students on 24-hour dietary recall may not be accurate, because some of the respondents could not remember accurately the foods and drinks eaten in the last 24 hours.
- ii. The dietary recall methodology may be biased which could be overestimated or underestimated of the food consumed in the previous day.
- iii. The food list used to collect data can be biased for true dietary intakes and may not reflect the routine diet pattern of respondents.

Conclusion

The results showed that some factors affect the food choices of the adolescents, such as the family dietary pattern, the finance, food availability and accessibility, hence, those with higher income purchase better quality foods and low income families purchase low quality foods. The findings of the study revealed that some of the respondents are underweight with low Body Mass Index. Some eat foods from fast food joints and some eat foods not adequate in protein. The study revealed that there was significant high

References

Afam-Anene, O., Ifenacho M. and Iwuchukwu N. O., (2015). Prevalence of Cardiovascular Diseases Risk factors among adults in Ozubulu. *Journal of Dieticians Association of Nigeria* 6 (2) 7-12.

level of positive relationship between the students' Body Mass Index and adolescent dietary diversity. The Dietary patterns of the adolescents are a public health concern because there is a direct association between inadequate diet at this early age and undernutrition. Therefore, adolescence is a good stage to intervene in changing dietary patterns to consolidate a healthy lifestyle that the adolescents will keep until adulthood and which in turn will transmit to healthy generation.

Recommendation

- i. There should be adolescent nutrition intervention programs that would address healthy diets and diversity of their diets.
- ii. Promoting dietary diversity patterns rich in essential nutrients like proteins, vitamins, and minerals, should be an important focus of nutrition programs.
- iii. School-based nutrition interventions programs should be prioritized to promote healthier eating behaviors among adolescents.
- iv. Nutrition educational activities that emphasizes on nutritional knowledge and awareness should be integrated into schools and communities programs

AL-Sharfi, M., (2015). "Psychological well-being and bullying/victimization among [adolescents](#) from polygamous and monogamous families in Saudi Arabia". *The European Conference on Psychology and the Behavioural Sciences, Brighton. United Kingdom*

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- Beck, A.L., Iturralde, E., Haya-Fisher, J., Kim, S., Keeton, V. and Fernandez, A., (2019). Barriers and facilitators to healthy eating among low-income Latino adolescents. *Appetite*; 138:215–222.
- Cosgrove, M., Flynn, A., and Kiely, M., (2005). Consumption of red meat, white meat and processed meat in Irish adults in relation to dietary quality. *Br J Nutr*; 93:933–942.
- Dambhare, D.G., Bharambe, M.S., Mehendale, A.M., Garg, B.S., (2010). Nutritional status and morbidity among school going adolescents in wardha, a peri-urban area. *Online J Health Allied Scs* 9: (2).
- Eshetu, A.A., (2015). Parental Soci-economic status as a determinant factor of academic performance of students in regional examination: a case of Dessie town, Ethiopia. *Afr Educ Res J*. 3(4):221–9.
- FAO, (2006). Baseline Survey Report Protecting and Improving Household Food Security and Nutrition in HIV/AIDS Affected Areas in Manica and Sofala Province, Maputo, Mozambique. (Available at http://www.foodsec.org/tr/nut/baseline_june07.pdf)
- Fitzgerald, A., Heary, C., Nixon, E. and Kelly, C. (2010): Factors influencing the food choices of Irish children & adolescents: A qualitative investigation. *Health Promotion International*. 25(3):289–298
- Gebreyohannes, Y., Solomon Shiferaw, S., Demtsu, B., Bugssa, G., (2014). Nutritional status of adolescents in selected government and private secondary schools of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Nutrition and Food Sciences*; 3(6):504–514.
- Gibson, R.S. and Ferguson, E.L., (2008). An Interactive 24-hour Recall for Assessing the Adequacy of Iron and Zinc Intakes in Developing Countries. <http://www.ifpri.org/sites/default/files/publications/tech08.pdf> (accessed July 2020).
- Gibson, R.S., Charrondiere, R. and Bell, W., (2017). Measurement errors in dietary assessment using self-reported 24-hour recalls in low-income countries and strategies for their prevention. *Adv Nitr* 8, 11
- Goon, D.T., Toriola, A.L., Shaw, B.S., Amusa, L.O. and Monyeke, M.A., (2011). Anthropometrically determined nutritional status of urban primary school children in Makurdi, Nigeria. *BMC Public Health* 11: 769.
- Jequier, E. and Constant, F., (2010). Water as an essential nutrient: the physiological basis of hydration. *Eur J Clin Nutr*; 64:115–123

Donald-Ase Mary, Akhigbe Evelyn Omolegho, Promise Vivian Ibienebakabobo, Alikali Ojochege Joy, *Allison Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Afam-Anene, Olivia

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<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ajcr/index>

- Lee, S. and Park, H., (2021). The Role of Public Health Campaigns in Promoting Hydration among Adolescents. *Public Health Nutrition*, 24(12), 3812-3820.
- Neumark-Sztainer, D., Wall, M., Larson, N.I., Eisenberg, M.E. and Loth, K., (2011). Dieting and disordered eating behaviors from adolescence to young adulthood: Findings from a 10-year longitudinal study. *Am Diet Assoc*; 111(7):1004–1011
- Saunders, J., (2010). Malnutrition: causes and consequences. *Clin Med (Lond)* 10(6):624–627
- Vaitkeviciute, R., Ball, L.E. and Harris N., (2015). The relationship between food literacy and dietary intake in adolescents: A systematic review. *Public Health Nutr*; 18:649–658
- Welch, A.A., Fransen, H., Jenab, M., Boutron-Ruault, M.C., Tumino, R. and Agnoli C., (2009). Variation in intakes of calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, iron and potassium in 10 countries in the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition study. *Eur J Clin Nutr*; 63(Suppl. 4):S101–S121.
- WHO and WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group, (2016). Reliability of Anthropometric Measurements in the WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study. *Acta Paediatrica*
- WHO, (2006). Global database on Body Mass Index: BMI Classification. Geneva: World Health Organization.
- World Health Organization (2017). Adolescent development. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/Organization> (2017). Adolescent development. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int>
- World Health Organization, (2012). Global Database on Body Mass Index. Archived from the original on April 18, 2009. Retrieved July 27,
- World Health Organization, (2012). Obesity and overweight. 2013. Available from: http://apps.who.int/bmi/index.jsp?introPage=intro_3.html. Accessed December 6, 2013

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